

Shannon's Entropy Using $\ln()$ and the Notion of Products of Probabilities

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Shannon's entropy is given by $-\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$, where $\ln(p(i))$ represents information which is said to add linearly in information theory, i.e. $F(p_1 * p_2) = F(p_1) + F(p_2)$. Information theory then seems to have been associated with the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) ideal gas for which e_i 's add and so $\text{constant} * e_i$ is information and $\ln(p_1 * p_2) = \ln(p_1) + \ln(p_2)$ which then leads to a sum of the conserved quantity.

Tsallis entropy, however, does not follow this pattern (but does arise from maximization of entropy subject to constraints) and so it seems that Shannon's entropy with its $\ln()$ function should apply to cases for which a product of probabilities arises physically and can be shown to represent additive information. For the MB case, this is straightforward because one has interactions represented by products of probabilities $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ and if $\ln(p(e_i)) = \text{constant} * e_i$, then this is additive.

It is possible, however, to utilize Shannon's entropy in other cases. For example, we consider two particles which must have a total energy of E . Maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to no constraints (because e and $E-e$ are included in the entropy expression) leads to a weight of $1/2$ for both e and $E-e$ which must be the case for no bias. In such a case, we ask: Why was Shannon's entropy used? There is no natural product of probabilities in this case. One could, however, imagine two sets of two particles and in such a case products of probabilities would arise naturally and $F(a * b) = F(a) + F(b)$, where F is the information function, does seem to make sense in such a case.

Shannon's $\ln()$ function, however, does not seem to make sense in all cases as it does not apply to the Tsallis case. In (1), we show that given constraints on average energy (e_i power 1 moment) and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ (e_i power 0 moment), one can define a general entropy $-\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ which consolidates $p(e_i)$ and the moments into one function $F(p(e_i))$ which is not necessarily the $\ln()$ function. In fact, two solutions are found, one is $\ln()$ and the other the Tsallis $F, (-1 + p^{1-q}) / (1-q)$.

Shannon's Entropy

Shannon's entropy arises in information theory (which is not necessarily physics) and introduces the notion of information contained in a probability, i.e.

$$F(p(i)) = \text{information linked with } p(i) \quad ((1))$$

A key idea is that:

$$F(p(i) * p(j)) = F(p(i)) + F(p(j)) \quad ((2))$$

This leads to $F = \ln(p(i))$ ((3)) as the information function.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Theory

The form of Shannon's entropy (from information theory) matches the the Maxwell-Boltzmann ideal gas case, because one may write:

$$S = - \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((4))$$

If ((4)) is maximized subject to

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave} \quad ((5))$$

then one obtains $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ ((6))

We have shown, however, in previous notes that ((6)) follows immediately from:

$$p(e_i) p(e_j) = p(e_i + e_j) = p(e_k) p(e_l) \quad \text{if} \quad e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l \quad ((7))$$

((7)) shows product probabilities appearing physically in a problem (i.e. the probability for an e_i to collide with an e_j is proportional to $p(e_i) * p(e_j)$ and one sees the notion of additive information if

$$\ln(p(e)) = \text{constant} * e \quad ((8))$$

We suggest, however, that this does not mean that one always uses Shannon's entropy. We argue that one must have a physical reason for having product probabilities and be able to argue that ((2)) indeed holds. We suggest that this is not always the case.

Tsallis Entropy

It is possible to create the notion of an information function $F(p(i))$, just as Shannon did and write its average:

$$\sum_i p(i) F(p(i)) \quad ((9))$$

One may even maximize ((9)) subject to constraints. In fact in (1), we argue that if $p(e_i)$ and one has the constraints ((5)) (just as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case) and insists that:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T + b \quad (b = \text{constant}) \quad ((10))$$

Then there are in fact two solutions:

$$F(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)) \quad (\text{the MB case}) \quad \text{and} \quad F(p(e_i)) = (-1 + p^{\text{power}(1-q)}) / (1-q) \quad ((11))$$

The second solution is the Tsallis case. It does not correspond to ((2)), but this distribution arises in nature. Thus, one does not always have additive information or natural products of probabilities, we argue.

A Case of Two Particles

We next consider the case of two particles whose total energy is E . If the first particle has energy e , the second has energy $E-e$. If the particles are identical and every e is equally likely, then one may assign $\frac{1}{2}$ to the first particle (probability) and $\frac{1}{2}$ to the other. Assigning $\frac{1}{3}$ to the first and $\frac{2}{3}$ to the second would result in an unexplainable bias.

One may show that this result follows from maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to no constraints i.e.

$$d/d/a \ a \ln(a) + (1-a) \ln(1-a) = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \ln(a/(1-a)) = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad a = \frac{1}{2} \quad ((12))$$

The question then becomes: Where is the product of probabilities and why should a linear sum of information hold? One would not naturally consider $a * (1-a)$. If, however, one had two sets of two particles, one would naturally have product probabilities in this case and:

$$F(a * b) = F(a) + F(b) \quad ((13)), \text{ we argue.}$$

Thus, it seems that Shannon's entropy (\ln for the information function) should hold in this case, as it seems to do.

We simply caution that one cannot always use: $F(a * b) = F(a) + F(b)$, even if one can define an entropy function and maximize it subject to constraints.

Conclusion

Shannon's entropy arose from information theory in which $F(a * b) = F(a) + F(b)$, where F is an information function and a and b , probabilities. This suggests that product probabilities apply naturally (physically) in a problem and that information for a product adds linearly. We suggest that in physical systems this is not always the case as shown in (1). For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, Shannon's entropy applies because $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) = e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$ and $\ln(p(e_i)) = \text{constant} * e_i$. In the Tsallis case, however, it does not apply.

We consider an example of two particles whose energies sum to 1 and argue that Shannon's entropy applies in such a case. As a result, $\ln()$ from Shannon's entropy does not need to arise from Stirling's approximation for a large number of particles. One may argue that if one has two sets of these two particles, then products of probabilities make sense and that $F(a * b) = F(a) + F(b)$ should hold.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. MaxEnt Versus $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$ (preprint, zendoo, 2026)